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METADISCOURSE MARKERS IN UNPUBLISHED RESEARCH PAPERS OF BASIC EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract

Metadiscourse markers enhance the clarity, coherence, and persuasiveness of research papers, improving their effectiveness in knowledge dissemination and professional development. This study employed a descriptive-quantitative research design to examine the use of metadiscourse markers in unpublished research papers of elementary and high school teachers in the Schools Division of Ilocos Sur, Philippines. A total of 112 research papers were analyzed, selected through purposive sampling. The analysis was conducted using Antconc concordance and Text Inspector tools, guided by Hyland's Metadiscourse Checklist. The findings revealed that high school teachers used more interactive markers, such as code glosses, evidential markers, frame markers, and transitions, compared to their elementary counterparts. The study also identified inappropriate, overused, and underused markers in the papers. To address these issues, a special training session was developed to help teachers integrate appropriate metadiscourse markers in their basic and action research writing.

Keywords: *Basic Education Teachers, Interactional markers, Interactive markers, Metadiscourse markers, Unpublished research papers*

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